

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Vasconcelos, G. F., & Almeida, V. (2024). Carbon credit and macaúba palm tree: Advancing ESG in green cattle production. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 28(5), e240116. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2024240116.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Vasconcelos, G. F., Almeida, V., & Russo, E. (2024). Peer review report for: Carbon credit and macaúba palm tree: Advancing ESG in green cattle production. RAC. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041180>

REVIEWERS:

- Eduardo Russo (Tecnológico de Monterrey, Business School, Mexico)
The other reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Eduardo Russo

Date review returned: May 28, 2024

Recommendation: Major revision

Comments to the authors

The case is interesting and aligned with the scope and focus of the journal. However, in my view, a significant effort still needs to be made by the authors to make the manuscript more attractive for publication. Below are some suggestions for improving the material.

I understand that the name Macaúba, for being a proper noun, should not be translated. In the title, I suggest

adding the word "palm tree" before the ":". The text needs to pass through an English revision, as some sentences are not coherent (e.g., "aiming to increase his income and that of the Community"). I suggest that the dialogues in the text be in italics to highlight the characters' speech. Words like "Fazenda" should be translated. The introduction of the case is somewhat confusing; I suggest rewriting this part to make it more objective. For example, until part 3, the relationship between the farm and the cattle business is not clear. Many pieces of information are presented abruptly, becoming tangled in the narrative proposed by the authors (cattle raising, reforestation, carbon credits, Macaúba palm trees, etc.), all within a few lines. This causes the reader to start the case feeling a little bit lost in what is being proposed.

Many financial data are presented throughout the text, indicating that the case could be applied to finance courses. However, the target audience of the case, as mentioned in the abstract, gives a different direction. It is important to present information in the case that aids in its discussion; any excess can be removed or presented as exhibits. The apparent lack of focus in the introduction seems to be a problem throughout all the case. Various initiative possibilities are presented without the necessary depth. For example, the eco-bungalows and oil exploitation of the palm trees are only mentioned briefly. Are the few data presented enough for students to reach the proposed level of analysis? This is a reflection the authors need to consider.

The endnotes do not follow APA or ABNT standards. In Appendix 1, some financial assumptions are presented. Wouldn't it be interesting to work with different scenarios? As it stands, it is assumed that all assumptions will be confirmed, without variations caused by external influences. It would be interesting to see greater objectivity in the case abstract as well. It is too long, attempting to address many things and a wide audience. I see the case as a niche product, and this segmentation, including the target audience, needs to be better defined. The target audience in the abstract differs from that presented in the learning objectives. I suggest separating the target audience from the learning objectives, addressing them in separate sections. For the learning objectives, I suggest using Bloom's Taxonomy.

It would be beneficial if the theoretical concepts presented by the authors were introduced throughout the discussion questions in the analysis part. I don't see how the introduction of various concepts in the current form (all loose) contributes to navigating the proposed discussion for the case, allowing the necessary theoretical links. In the discussion plan, for a class of how many minutes is this case suggested? The case lacks assignment questions, which still need to be created. The opening discussion question presents suggested possible answers containing information that cannot be inferred from what is presented in the case. There is no theoretical discussion (authors) throughout the proposed discussion questions. Thank you for the opportunity to read your material, and good luck.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: No

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).: None.

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 3. Average
Originality: 2. Good
Overall: 3. Average

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Responses

Dear Dr. Paula Chimenti, Editor-in-Chief of Revista de Administração Contemporânea,

Thank you for handling our manuscript now titled “Carbon Credit & Macaúba Palm Tree: Advancing ESG in Green Cattle Production” and offering thoughtful and constructive suggestions for moving forward. We have paid close attention to both reviewers’ comments and strengthened the manuscript accordingly.

The abstract, introduction, and objectives have been thoroughly revised to improve clarity and coherence. We made sure that they align well with the overall purpose of the case while also incorporating additional information into the case to enable students to address the questions proposed more effectively. This includes expanding on key details and providing necessary context for deeper analysis. We also reviewed and corrected the endnotes following the reviewers’ suggestions to enhance the overall quality of the manuscript. Finally, we included figures as an appendix.

We remain fully committed to addressing any further comments and suggestions to improve the quality and contribution of this study. The section below documents point-by-point responses to each reviewer.

Yours sincerely,

The authors.

Dear Reviewers,

Thank you very much for your constructive and thoughtful feedback. Addressing your comments has substantially enhanced the quality of the manuscript. Please refer below to the point-by-point actions we took to address each of the observations put forward by both reviewers.

Reviewer 1

Comments:

The case is interesting and aligned with the scope and focus of the journal. However, in my view, a significant effort still needs to be made by the authors to make the manuscript more attractive for publication. Below are some suggestions for improving the material. Thank you for your thorough review and valuable feedback on our manuscript. We appreciate your positive remarks about the alignment of our case study with the scope and focus of the journal. We have carefully considered your suggestions and have made several improvements to enhance the quality and attractiveness of our manuscript. Below we address each of your points in detail.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your thorough review and valuable feedback on our manuscript. We appreciate your positive remarks about the alignment of our case study with the scope and focus of the journal. We have carefully considered your suggestions and have made several improvements to enhance the quality and attractiveness of our manuscript. Below we address each of your points in detail.

Comments:

I understand that the name Macaúba, for being a proper noun, should not be translated. In the title, I suggest adding the word "palm tree" before the ":".

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for highlighting the issue regarding the translation of the term "Macaúba". We have added the term "palm tree" in the title. The revised title now reads: "Carbon Credit & Macaúba Palm Tree: Advancing ESG in Green Cattle Production" [Page 1].

Comments:

The text needs to pass through an English revision, as some sentences are not coherent (e.g., "aiming to increase his income and that of the Community").

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for pointing out the need for an English revision to address coherence issues in our manuscript.

We have thoroughly revised the text to improve its coherence and clarity. Specifically this sentence has been revised to "He knew, however, that increasing the community's income would involve a significant partnership among the farm, the local residents, and a third party". [Page 1]

Comments:

I suggest that the dialogues in the text be in italics to highlight the characters' speech.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your suggestion. We agree that this formatting change will improve the readability and clarity of the dialogues. We have revised the manuscript accordingly.

[...] "... what about engaging with Reflora? The enterprise has shown enthusiasm for investing in carbon credit projects here on the farm. In particular, they expressed a notable interest in reforestation with the Macaúba palm, which is underutilized here on the farm." [Page 1]

Comments:

Words like "Fazenda" should be translated.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your suggestion regarding the translation of the word "Fazenda".

We have reviewed the manuscript and translated "Fazenda" to "farm". For instance, "Cachoeirinha Farm" in [Page 1, 2, 5, 8, 11, 12, 14].

Comments:

The introduction of the case is somewhat confusing; I suggest rewriting this part to make it more objective. For example, until part 3, the relationship between the farm and the cattle business is not clear. Many pieces of information are presented abruptly, becoming tangled in the narrative proposed by the authors (cattle raising, reforestation, carbon credits, Macaúba palm trees, etc.), all within a few lines. This causes the reader to start the case feeling a little bit lost in what is being proposed.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback. We revised the introduction to present the information more coherently, ensuring that the relationship between the farm and the cattle business is clearer and the narrative flow is smoother. Some sentences have been added to the text:

“They spent some time discussing various possibilities for expanding the farm's business. They considered creating a tourist area on part of the farm where they could build bungalows for sale. They also thought of taking advantage of the existing number of Macaúba palm trees to produce and sell oil from the Macaúba fruit.

As Jules sipped a hot cup of coffee, he began to think about his desire to see the local community grow along with the farm. Jules had a deep affection for the community where he lived and felt sorry for the few opportunities local residents had to improve their lives. He knew, however, that increasing the community's income would involve a significant partnership among the farm, the local residents, and a third party.” [Page 1]

Comments:

Many financial data are presented throughout the text, indicating that the case could be applied to finance courses. However, the target audience of the case, as mentioned in the abstract, gives a different direction.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

We appreciate your suggestion. We have revised the abstract to better align with the financial focus of the case.

“The case can be applied in undergraduate and graduate level courses in Finance and related fields. The case is recommended to encourage students to reflect on the financial structures and challenges of implementing the sale of carbon credits for small rural landowners.” [Page 9]

Comments:

It is important to present information in the case that aids in its discussion; any excess can be removed or presented as exhibits.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback. We have addressed this concern by revising the case to ensure that relevant information is presented in the main text [Pages 1 to 5]. Any additional details that were previously included have been moved to the appendixes [Page 6, 7].

Comments:

The apparent lack of focus in the introduction seems to be a problem throughout all the case. Various initiative possibilities are presented without the necessary depth. For example, the eco-bungalows and oil exploitation of the palm trees are only mentioned briefly.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your comments. We have addressed the issue of focus in the case by revising the introduction to provide clearer guidance and context.

We have also expanded the sections on the eco-bungalows and the oil exploitation of the Macaúba palms, offering more detailed analyses and depth to these initiatives. For example:

“Jules also evaluated an alternative project to build ecological bungalows on the farm. The farm's proximity to a national preservation area and the opportunity for close nature experiences were quite attractive. A designated area could be allocated for developing these bungalows to create a luxury condominium. In this case, Jules intended to invite local community members to build restaurants and offer guided tours within the community, enhancing the overall experience for visitors while providing economic opportunities for residents. However, the construction could be complex due to strict regulations and permits, making the investment process time-consuming. Jules needed to carefully consider the environmental impacts, adhere to construction restrictions, and manage waste properly. For this project, Jules estimated a per-unit investment of US\$ 60,000 paired with a maintenance fee of US\$ 100 per unit. He projected a potential selling price of US\$ 88,000 per bungalow after accounting for a sales commission fee of 8%. Jules intended to personally finance all the capital expenditures, including infrastructure development and utilities. While this approach would give him greater control over the project, it also meant shouldering significant upfront and ongoing expenses.” [Page 3]

“After considering this expansion option, the partners consulted with Professor Leonardo from the Federal University of Viçosa, who guided them on profiting from using the Macaúba palm coconut to produce processed oil. Jules would have abundant Macaúba palm resources, ensuring a sustainable and accessible supply of raw material for oil production. The growing market demand for Macaúba oil in industries such as cosmetics, food, and biofuels could present a promising opportunity to diversify income streams and reduce reliance on a single investment. Considering a 198-acre plot, they estimated an initial investment of US\$ 300,000, with maintenance costs of 2% of revenue and annual depreciation of US \$10,000. Sales, general, and administrative costs would constitute 12% of expenses with a working capital requirement of US\$ 24,000. The partners would be subject to a 0.25% tax on the farm and an 18% sales tax. Initially, it was decided that each partner would contribute equally to the investment costs and to the revenue obtained. There was a risk that they would need another investor, which could be both time-consuming and challenging to secure.

Finally, the professor also explained that the market for Macaúba oil could face competition from other vegetable oils, requiring careful assessment of the competitive landscape and demand levels. Furthermore, Macaúba oil prices could be volatile, thus affecting profitability, and Jules needed to be cautious of the risks associated with monoculture practices.” [Page 5]

Comments:

Are the few data presented enough for students to reach the proposed level of analysis? This is a reflection the authors need to consider.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for raising this concern. We have reviewed and expanded the case study to ensure that it provides adequate data for students to engage in the proposed level of analysis. Additional information and details [Pages 1 to 5] have been included to enhance the depth and breadth of the case, addressing the need for a more comprehensive examination of the various business opportunities and their implications.

Comments:

The endnotes do not follow APA or ABNT standards.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for pointing that out. We revised the endnotes to ensure they adhere to the appropriate APA format: [Page 6]

1 Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística, IBGE (2023). População. Retrieved August 4th, 2023 from <<https://cidades.ibge.gov.br/brasil/mg/olaria/panorama>>.

2 Federal University of Viçosa, UFV (2023). University. Retrieved October 2nd, 2023 from <<https://www.ufv.br>>.

3 The Nature Conservancy, TNC (2023). Restaurar ecossistemas para combater mudanças climáticas. Retrieved August 14th, 2023 from <<https://www.tnc.org.br>>.

4 Refflora (2023). REFLORA Programme. Retrieved August 14th, 2023 from <<https://floradobrasil.jbrj.gov.br/reflora/PrincipalUC/PrincipalUC.do;jsessionid=875B23AA11A7A252218625048F5EDE01>>.

5 Brasil (2012). Law No. 12.651/2012 – Proteção da Vegetação Nativa. Retrieved November 25th, 2023 from <https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2012/lei/12651.htm>.

Comments:

In Appendix 1, some financial assumptions are presented. Wouldn't it be interesting to work with different scenarios? As it stands, it is assumed that all assumptions will be confirmed, without variations caused by external influences.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your suggestion. As you can see on page 17, we indicated that different scenarios are indeed intended to be considered: "The instructor may now delve into a sensitivity analysis using the previously mentioned scenarios."

But, to ensure that this is more clearly highlighted, we have added the following passage to the text:

"Next, students can be encouraged to think about other factors that could also affect Jules' decision. The professor can ask students to think about different scenarios to analyze the sensitivity of the assumptions used or consider the qualitative factors that can also impact the decision analysis." [Page 17]

Comments:

It would be interesting to see greater objectivity in the case abstract as well. It is too long, attempting to address many things and a wide audience. I see the case as a niche product, and this segmentation, including the target audience, needs to be better defined.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback. We revised the abstract to focus more specifically on the target audience and the core objectives of the case. The updated abstract now reads:

"The case can be applied in undergraduate and graduate level courses in Finance and related fields. The case is recommended to encourage students to reflect on the financial structures and challenges of implementing the sale of carbon credits for small rural landowners." [Page 9]

Comments:

The target audience in the abstract differs from that presented in the learning objectives. I suggest separating the target audience from the learning objectives, addressing them in separate sections. For the learning objectives, I suggest using Bloom's Taxonomy.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback. We have revised the abstract and the learning objectives to align them more closely with the target audience. You can read now: "This case was developed to be used in undergraduate and graduate level courses in the field of Finance. The case can be applied during sections that address the concepts related to decision-making in sustainable problems". [Page 10]

The learning objectives were also revised according to Bloom's Taxonomy to ensure a structured and comprehensive approach:

a) Explain the profitability of reforesting land with Macaúba palms, assessing their potential as a distinct asset class.

b) Calculate the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) for each business opportunity related to the Cachoeirinha farm.

c) Use both quantitative and qualitative critical thinking skills to analyze the business model for selling carbon credits on rural properties and its feasibility.

d) Assess the potential positive externalities of carbon credit sales for Jules and the local community considering the broader social and environmental impacts.” [Page 10]

Comments:

It would be beneficial if the theoretical concepts presented by the authors were introduced throughout the discussion questions in the analysis part. I don't see how the introduction of various concepts in the current form (all loose) contributes to navigating the proposed discussion for the case, allowing the necessary theoretical links.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your comment. To address this issue we have added suggested readings and literature associated with each discussion question. For instance,

“To prepare the students for the discussions and enrich the debate, the instructor can choose to present the concepts of financial viability as presented by Damodaram (2012) and Magni (2020), among others. Also, environmental considerations can be supported after a literature review of Carnell (2010) and Oliveira Silva et al. (2016), among others.” [Page 13 – Question 1]

“To answer this question in more depth, the instructor can suggest that the students read Dohrn (2013) and Zainal's (2021) work” [Page 15 – Question 2]

“In this case, the work of Carnell (2010) and Colombo et al. (2018) can help students gain a deeper understanding of the topic” [Page 17 – Question 3]

Comments:

In the discussion plan, for a class of how many minutes is this case suggested?

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your comment. The case is suggested for a class duration of 120 to 150 minutes. This information is more clearly highlighted in Table 1 of the teaching plan. [Page 11]

Comments:

The case lacks assignment questions, which still need to be created.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

In fact, due to the nature of this case, the discussion questions can be used as assignment questions, so we made this recommendation clear:

It is supposed that the students will receive and prepare the case before meeting in class. The teacher can, at his/her discretion, use the case discussion questions as assignment questions, which can be given to students along with the case to guide them in individual prior preparation. [Page 11]

Comments:

The opening discussion question presents suggested possible answers containing information that cannot be inferred from what is presented in the case.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback. To address this concern we added more information throughout the case [Pages 1 to 5], such as the following paragraph:

“Jules would have abundant Macaúba palm resources, ensuring a sustainable and accessible supply of raw material for oil production. The growing market demand for Macaúba oil in industries such as cosmetics, food, and biofuels could present a promising opportunity to diversify income streams and reduce reliance on a single investment. Considering a 198-acre plot, they estimated an initial investment of US\$ 300,000 with maintenance costs of 2% of revenue and annual depreciation of US\$ \$10,000. Sales, general, and administrative costs would constitute 12% of expenses with a working capital requirement of US\$ 24,000. The partners would be subject to a 0.25% tax on the farm and an 18% sales tax. Initially, it was decided that each partner would contribute equally to the investment costs and to the revenue obtained. There was a risk that they would need another investor, which could be both time-consuming and challenging to secure.

Finally, the professor also explained that the market for Macaúba oil could face competition from other vegetable oils, requiring careful assessment of the competitive landscape and demand levels. Furthermore, Macaúba oil prices could be volatile, thus affecting profitability, and Jules needed to be cautious of the risks associated with monoculture practices.” [Page 5]

Comments:

There is no theoretical discussion (authors) throughout the proposed discussion questions.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback. We made the necessary changes to include theoretical discussions and references to relevant authors throughout the proposed discussion questions. For example:

“To prepare the students for the discussions and enrich the debate, the instructor can choose to present the concepts of financial viability as presented by Damodaram (2012) and Magni (2020), among others. Also, environmental considerations can be supported after a literature review of Carnell (2010) and Oliveira Silva et al. (2016), among others.” [Page 13 – Question 1]

“”To answer this question in more depth, the instructor can suggest that the students read Dohrn (2013) and Zainal’s (2021) work” [Page 15 – Question 2]

“In this case, the work of Carnell (2010) and Colombo et al. (2018) can help students gain a deeper understanding of the topic” [Page 16 – Question 3]

Comments:

Thank you for the opportunity to read your material, and good luck.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript:

Thank you for your feedback and for taking the time to review our material. We appreciate your well wishes and are grateful for your input.

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 2**Reviewer 1 report**

Reviewer: Eduardo Russo

Date review returned: August 16, 2024

Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

Ultimately, teaching cases are designed to allow the skills developed from discussing the case to be extrapolated and replicated in other related situations. For this reason, learning objectives should not be specific to the case context but rather addressed more broadly. Only objective c follows this logic, while all others still require adjustments. I still do not like the idea of using discussion questions as assignment questions. As I mentioned earlier, they serve different purposes, and therefore, they should not be the same. The gap between theory and analysis persists. There was an attempt to correct this; however, from my perspective, it was not sufficient. Presenting texts where the instructor can find the concepts without presenting them is the same as only having a suggested bibliography section. In my opinion, these three points still need to be addressed before the material is ready for publication.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: None.

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Good

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Responses

Dear Dr. Paula Chimenti, Editor-in-Chief of Revista de Administração Contemporânea,

Thank you for overseeing our manuscript. We appreciate your acknowledgment of our efforts to address the reviewers' points.

We have carefully revisited the manuscript and made the necessary revisions, specifically focusing on bridging the theory with the analysis of the case as you suggested. We believe these changes enhance the clarity and coherence of our work.

We are dedicated to addressing any additional comments and suggestions to improve the quality and impact of this study. Below, we provide a detailed point-by-point response to each reviewer.

Yours sincerely,

The authors.

Dear Reviewers,

We sincerely appreciate your valuable and insightful feedback. Your comments have significantly improved the quality of the manuscript. Below, we outline the specific actions we took in response to each observation raised by both reviewers.

Reviewer 1

Comments:

Ultimately, teaching cases are designed to allow the skills developed from discussing the case to be extrapolated and replicated in other related situations. For this reason, learning objectives should not be specific to the case context but rather addressed more broadly. Only objective c follows this logic, while all others still require adjustments.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript

Thank you for your thoughtful feedback on our manuscript. We have ensured that the learning objectives align with Bloom's taxonomy. We have added the following statement to the manuscript:

"The discussion of this case enables the development of the six skills of the cognitive domain according to the original taxonomy proposed by Bloom (Bloom, 1956), namely: a) knowledge, recalling of theories and concepts; b) comprehension, understanding whether by interpretation or extrapolation; c) application of financial rules, methods and models; d) analysis of case alternatives; e) synthesis of the problem situation; and f) evaluation of the situation and proposal of an action plan."
[Page 10]

Comments:

I still do not like the idea of using discussion questions as assignment questions. As I mentioned earlier, they serve different purposes, and therefore, they should not be the same.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript

Thank you for your continued feedback on our manuscript. We appreciate your perspective regarding the distinction between discussion questions and assignment questions.

In response to your comment, we have added a dedicated "Assignment Questions" section to the manuscript. The passage included in this section is as follows:

“Assignment Questions

It is supposed that the students will receive and prepare the case before meeting in class. The teacher can, at his/her discretion, provide students with the listed Assignment Questions (AQ) along with the case, to guide them in individual prior preparation.

- AQ 1: Should the pursuit of profit in reforestation efforts be considered beneficial, or is it more appropriate for governments and private philanthropists to take responsibility for reforestation?

- AQ 2: What would be the real benefits for the environment and the local community of the Cachoeirinha farm?

- AQ 3: Is it possible to reconcile profitability with social and environmental responsibility in the case of the Cachoeirinha farm?

- AQ 4: As a friend of Jules, would you recommend investing in carbon sales? Why?”

[Page 10]

Comments:

The gap between theory and analysis persists. There was an attempt to correct this; however, from my perspective, it was not sufficient. Presenting texts where the instructor can find the concepts without presenting them is the same as only having a suggested bibliography section.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript

Thank you for your constructive feedback regarding the gap between theory and analysis in our manuscript. We acknowledge your concerns and understand that our previous attempts did not sufficiently address this issue.

To better bridge the gap, we removed the Theoretical Section and incorporated a more thorough integration of theoretical concepts directly within the questions analysis. The text can now be seen as:

“To prepare the students for the discussions and enrich the debate, the instructor can choose to present the concepts of financial viability. The financial viability principles apply to the farm's operations. Jules expresses his concerns about his property's financial sustainability, emphasizing the need to diversify his income avenues. An understanding of NPV and IRR empowers students to evaluate the financial soundness of various initiatives and to project the potential profitability of the farm's investments. Net present value (NPV) is the difference between the present value of cash inflows and the present value of cash outflows over a period of time. Its formula is given by equation 1, where C_t is the net cash inflow during the period t ($t=1 \dots T$) and C_0 is the total initial investment costs.

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+i)^t} - C_0 \quad (1)$$

By contrast, the internal rate of return (IRR) is a calculation used to estimate the profitability of potential investments. Its formula is given by equation 2.

$$0 = NPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+i)^t} - C_0 \quad (2)$$

For a richer awareness of NPV and IRR, we suggest the readings by Damodaram (2012) and Magni (2020). Moreover, we recommend supplemental readings for an in-depth exploration of Jules' operational segments such as studies by Ruviano et al. (2020) and Cardoso et al. (2016) on cattle production as well as the work of Pegas & Castley (2014) for insights into eco-tourism.

Also, environmental considerations can be supported after a literature review of Carnell (2010) and Oliveira Silva et al. (2016). This pillar is associated with the role of reforestation for-profit using the Macaúba palm tree, emphasizing the significance of diminishing carbon footprints in contemporary agriculture and its ramifications on climate change. Initially, we advise instructors to guide students toward literature emphasizing the urgency of curtailing carbon dioxide emissions, providing a particular focus on Brazil's contributions. Exploring ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) readings will enable students to connect with the farm's dedication to sustainability, for which Cerri et al. (2009) come highly recommended. Subsequent readings might include insights on reforestation and farmer responsibilities, referencing works such as Pinto (2010).” [Pages 12 and 13]

“To answer this question in more depth, the instructor can suggest that the students read Dohrn (2013) and Zainal's (2021) work. These readings can help the instructor to frame the transition to sustainable production systems as an environmental conservation strategy and a catalyst for community growth. The focus is on the social pillar of ESG, key areas include improving community welfare via urban farming, using informal socialization methods such as Word of Mouth (WoM), and leveraging collaboration with governmental and private entities. These initiatives can be a model for community-driven economic development, despite challenges like limited resources and land.

Similarly, these articles emphasize sustainable agricultural practices that contribute to environmental conservation, while also fostering community development through job creation and improved living standards. Additionally, it addresses the cultural preservation aspect by supporting local heritage and traditional farming practices. Thus, both works provide rich material to explore topics such as community-driven sustainability, collaborative efforts between government and private sectors, and the broader impact of small-scale initiatives on local economies and ecosystems.” [Page 15]

“In this case, the work of Carnell (2010) can help students gain a deeper understanding of the topic. Additionally, for insights into the particulars of carbon credit sales by farmers, Ribeiro, Jacovine & Vilar's (2012) article is a good suggestion. Carbon credits are permits that represent the right to emit a specific amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) or other greenhouse gases (GHGs). One carbon credit typically corresponds to one metric ton of CO₂ or its equivalent in other GHGs. They are part of market-based approaches aimed at reducing overall greenhouse gas emissions and combating climate change.

Also, we suggest an analysis of the Macaúba palm tree and its byproducts, drawing on the research from Colombo et al. (2018), Fernández-Coppel et al. (2018), and Cabrera (2022). The Macaúba palm tree (*Acrocomia aculeata*), native to South America, is a valuable plant known for its versatility and resilience in tropical climates. It produces a range of byproducts, including oil from its fruit, which is used for cooking, cosmetics, and biodiesel; edible fruits; natural fibers for crafts and ropes; and timber for construction. Additionally, the byproducts of oil extraction serve as protein-rich animal feed. The cultivation of the Macaúba palm supports sustainable development, contributes to carbon sequestration, and aids in restoring degraded lands.” [Page 17]

Comments:

In my opinion, these three points still need to be addressed before the material is ready for publication.

Comments/Changes included in the manuscript

Thank you for your feedback. We appreciate your diligence in reviewing our manuscript. We have carefully addressed all the questions raised and believe that the necessary revisions have been made.

Your insights are invaluable in ensuring the quality of our work. Thank you again for your thorough review

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

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